

A SYSTEMATIC PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF DEVICES CAPABLE OF DELIVERING CPAP THERAPY IN A CLOSED-LOOP CONFIGURATION

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Introduction

Non-Invasive Ventilation (NIV), including continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) therapy, is vital for managing respiratory failure without the need for endotracheal intubation or tracheotomy [1]. However, the traditional open-loop configuration presents notable drawbacks, i.e., high daily oxygen consumption, risk of viral load contamination of the surrounding environment, and elevated noise levels [2]. To address these challenges, CPAP closed-loop configurations were proposed in recent years [3]. However, there is still a knowledge gap regarding its performance compared to the standard CPAP delivery technologies. The aim of this study is a systematic evaluation of pressure performances of devices able to deliver CPAP in both open and closed-loop configurations, aiming to ascertain if the latter can uphold comparable efficacy to commonly utilized standard configurations.

Methods

Four ventilation devices, including two obstructive sleep apnoea devices (O1, O2) and two ventilators (V1, V2), were tested in both open and closed-loop configurations. Experimental tests were conducted connecting the devices to a lung simulator (TestChest V3, Organics GmbH) and a flow analyser (FlowAnalyser Pro, IMT Analytics), and the therapy was delivered to a head phantom through the patient interface (full-face mask and helmet). All the tests were performed prescribe three different CPAP therapy levels (P_{Set} : 5, 7.5 and 10 cmH₂O) simulating three subject conditions normally treated with CPAP therapy: healthy, post-surgical and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS). In total, 192 tests were carried out, where the CPAP performances were compared in terms of: (1) mean static pressure (P_{mean}) measured at the patient interface when the lung simulator is off; (2) dynamic oscillations (ΔP), calculated as the difference between maximum and minimum pressure, measured at the patient interface.

Results

Closing the circuit globally leads to a P_{mean} reduction, with major impact when the mask is used (-1.3 cmH₂O on average for the mask against -0.3 cmH₂O on average for the helmet). This reduction is scarcely affected by P_{Set} (Fig. 1). Moreover, closing the CPAP circuit invariably leads to an increase in ΔP , with an average rise of 50% compared to the corresponding open CPAP circuit. In some cases, ΔP increments up to three times have been observed. Conversely, increasing the patient interface volume (i.e., replacing the mask with the

helmet) always reduces the ΔP value, with decrements ranging from 10% to 64%.

Figure 1: Pressure performances represented in box plot form: the intermediate line is P_{mean} , the box height is ΔP . The red line is the set CPAP (P_{Set}). MO: mask interface with the open circuit; MC: mask interface with the closed-loop circuit; HO: helmet interface with the open circuit; HC: helmet interface with the closed-loop circuit.

Discussion

In closed-loop configurations P_{mean} , indicating devices capability to deliver the set therapeutic pressure, deviates from P_{Set} , but this effect is reduced adopting the helmet as interface. Looking at pressure oscillations (representing devices reactivity), closing the circuit increases ΔP , but this effect can be compensated by using the helmet as interface. In conclusion, adopting a larger interface confers to the closed-loop configuration performances similar, and often with lower pressure oscillations, with respect to the traditional open-loop configuration.

References

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